

Developing local content-based teaching materials for improving students' holistic reading

Husni Mubarak^{1,2}, Sofyan Anif¹, Harun Joko Prayitno¹

¹Education Doctoral Program, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta, Surakarta, Indonesia

²Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teaching Sciences, Universitas Islam Nahdlatul Ulama Jepara, Jepara, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Integrating local content into teaching materials greatly aids students in their English learning, but the lack of such materials remains an issue. This study aims to develop teaching materials based on local content. It focuses on four key areas: needs analysis, development, practicality, and effectiveness. Utilizing the ADDIE or analysis, design, development, implementation and evaluation research design, data collection was conducted with seventh-grade students in the Jepara through observation, interview, questionnaire, and test, which were then analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative method. The analysis revealed that both students and teachers required teaching materials that incorporated local content. The validation of teaching materials indicated a score of 3.56 for lecturers and 3.74 for practitioners, categorizing it as very feasible. The practicality of the teaching materials is indicated by an observation score of 3.4 and a questionnaire score of 3.21. Students' holistic reading skills improved after utilizing teaching materials centered on local content, particularly in relation to their learning experiences, discourses, and reading comprehension. The findings suggest that the government should develop policies focused on utilizing local content in teaching materials.

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Corresponding Author:

Husni Mubarak

Education Doctoral Program, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education

Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta

A. Yani, Pabelan, Kartasura, Sukoharjo, Central Java, 57169, Indonesia

Email: q300230002@student.ums.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

English learning at junior high school level in Merdeka curriculum is currently in phase D. This phase aims to improve both oral and written language skills [1], as well as receptive and productive skills [2]. Additionally, it focuses on developing intercultural competence to foster understanding and respect for local and foreign cultures [1]. In actuality, the progress of English learning in schools has not been entirely successful. This happens because teachers have a small selection of teaching materials when they are teaching. Teachers frequently encounter challenges when creating teaching materials because they may lack adequate knowledge, training, and references [3]. Additionally, a lack of teacher competence can also contribute to these difficulties [4]. However, the utilization of current learning materials has not effectively fostered the enhancement of students' linguistic capabilities and proficiency in communication [5]. The learning materials used by teachers currently do not align with the curriculum and learning methods being utilized [6], [7].

The use of student worksheets is still prevalent in schools for English language learning. However, the current teaching materials lack a connection between the material's content and the local context and values. They do not take into account appropriate learning approaches that align with the characteristics of English subjects.

As a result, the reading skills of students continue to be poor, which is evident through the average score in English subjects during the assessment. The latest publication of the 2022 Program for International Students Assessment (PISA) report indicates a decline of 12 points in reading proficiency for students when comparing to the previous PISA scores in 2018 [8]. The weak ability of students to use spoken language effectively in different situations and understand written texts from different cultural backgrounds is evident in their limited literacy skills, as revealed through their use of different text types. However, students have not yet been able to acquire comprehensive skills in reading comprehension. They still rely on individual elements such as sound, vocabulary, sentences, and meaning, and struggle to fully grasp the overall theme or message of a text; spoken or written communication.

In order to address the issues mentioned earlier, it is important to have suitable teaching materials. The teaching materials that are prepared should have different types of illustrations, such as assignments, exercises, and other activities to promote comprehension of the material and enhance students' skills [9]. The activities organized in the advanced textbook are based on the collaborative learning method that takes place through conversation and cooperation or collaboration among both students and teachers [10]. In the implementation of collaborative learning methods, teachers need to possess high intelligence, display creativity, and demonstrate innovation when fostering critical thinking abilities for problem-solving [11]. The collaborative learning suggests that students who struggle to understand a concept on their own can improve their mastery of it with the assistance of others and eventually become capable of practicing it independently.

The placement of English learning goals in the curriculum not only helps students acquire English as a foreign language [12], but also necessitates that they engage with local cultural elements [1] and existing national culture [13]. Local content and language are interconnected, as culture is an inherent aspect of language. In light of this, the textbooks utilized in classroom instruction not only feature English as a foreign language content but also incorporate local content [14]. The term local pertains specifically to a designated area that caters to the diverse styles, preferences, cultural identities, and backgrounds of students [15]. Local content refers to teaching materials that highlight the distinct characteristics and potential of local regions, encompassing areas such as arts and culture, crafts, language, and more. It is also viewed as a distinct culture within a region that expresses the lifestyle of its inhabitants through their traditions, arts, cuisine, and more [16]. Moreover, in educational settings that embrace local content, students' cultural backgrounds, values, and viewpoints are seen as valuable contributions that enhance the learning experience [17]. The adaptation of materials is crucial in English language learning as it enables students to explore the local content and the diversity of their surroundings. The Jepara community continues to uphold its local cultural traditions to this day. One example is wood carving [18], which showcases their artistic talents and can also have a positive impact on the economy. Furthermore, some of them also engage in fishing [19], leading to the *Lomban* tradition (a fishing community tradition in Jepara, Indonesia that involves a sea alms, a buffalo head *larungan*, and a competition at Kartini Beach), which serves as a way to express appreciation for the plentiful marine resources. Notable places in Jepara also showcase the creative works of the local community, including wooden furniture, *monel* items, and *troso* cloth [20].

The importance of reading cannot be overstated as it directly correlates with students' academic success. The capacity to comprehend and interpret texts across different situations plays a crucial role in determining their achievements in education [21]. In addition to facilitating effective communication between ideas and readers, the primary objective of reading is to equip students with the necessary skills and strategies to gather information from different print sources [22]. To promote reading, it is important to take into account various factors such as how often people read, the quantity and diversity of reading material available, and the presence of guidelines or rules [23]. The holistic idea in reading stems from the whole language theory, which views language as a complete entity rather than just individual components such as speech sounds or separate grammar rules [24], [25]. This means that various factors, such as the people using the language, the situation they are in, their intentions, their social background, and the language rules they follow, all contribute to the inseparability of language. The qualities of holistic reading are demonstrated by using real-world teaching materials, engaging in activities that encompass all aspects of language skills, presenting teaching materials that are interconnected and refer to meaningful conversations, relating the materials to the actual context of students for practical application, and fostering collaborative learning between students or between students and teachers.

Previous research findings indicate that there is a shortage of teaching materials for English learning. One issue is the absence of materials that reflect local culture [26], [27], leading students to be less engaged with their culture [15], as they are not aware of the values present in those cultures [28]. Moreover, the existing teaching materials primarily emphasize on reading comprehension [23], [29] and the development of students' critical thinking skills [30], [31]. Nevertheless, there are currently no teaching materials available that highlight the rich cultural heritage of Jepara, which are still maintained today. Additionally, there are no materials designed to help students in enhancing their holistic reading skills. This research intends to: i) identify the need of teaching materials; ii) create local content-based teaching materials; iii) assess the practicality of the teaching materials; and iv) evaluate their impact on students' holistic reading.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study employs a research and development as it generates and verifies teaching materials as products [32]. The research process includes several stages known as ADDIE, which include analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation [33]. During the analysis phase, researchers carried out field studies to gather information and develop product plans that aim to resolve research issues. The process of gathering data for needs analysis involved observing how students learn, conducting interviews with teachers, and administering questionnaires to students. At this point, the findings from the analysis of the product development needs would be acquired. During the design phase, the researcher identifies the respondents being studied, establishes the goal of learning, formulates goals for learning, organizes the necessary materials, and plans engaging activities for learning. During the development phase, there are three activities conducted, which include creating preliminary teaching materials, receiving feedback from English lecturers and educational practitioners as expert validators, and making necessary revisions. Drafting is conducted in four stages, which involve determining indicators, creating teaching materials, preparing learning activities, and preparing practice questions.

The objective of design validation is to gather feedback, recommendations, and insights on the teaching materials under development. During the product validation phase, predetermined expert validators are fully involved. After confirming the accuracy of the design, the researcher incorporated modifications that were influenced by evaluations and feedback provided by English lecturers and educational practitioners. The revision can take various forms such as changing the content and materials used in teaching, creating new learning activities and exercises, improving the appearance and layout, updating images, and more. This product was tested during the implementation phase, specifically in extensive experiment. This study aimed to assess the suitability of the developing product, which consisted of local content-based teaching materials. Product modifications were implemented subsequent to researchers conducting limited experiments. At the evaluation stage, product assessment is carried out through evaluation stages which are carried out on groups of students on a larger scale than extensive experiment to obtain the effectiveness of the product being developed. The research utilized an experimental design.

2.2. Respondents

The study involved a sample of 158 students, selected based on the Krejcie and Morgan's formula [34] with an error margin of 5%, and two English teachers who served as respondents. Respondents were chosen through a random sampling method, taking into account the students' grade level, specifically seventh grade, as well as the teacher's experience in teaching English to seventh graders. This research took place in secondary schools situated in Jepara Regency, which is part of Central Java Province, Indonesia. Jepara Regency was selected as the research site due to its rich preservation of local culture such as influential figures, notable places, and traditional cuisine and the embodiment of its inherent values like the fight against colonialism and ignorance, expressions of gratitude in *Larung* tradition (a ceremony performed at sea as a form of respect and purification) at the beach, and food security and health through traditional cuisine.

2.3. Data collection and analysis

This research utilized two different methods for analyzing data. Firstly, a qualitative approach was used to analyze information gathered from observation and interview. Secondly, a quantitative approach was employed to analyze data obtained from questionnaire and test in the form of multiple choice. Qualitative research applies the stages of Miles and Huberman [35], which involve data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. At the same time, descriptive statistics are employed for quantitative analysis to examine the data obtained from the questionnaire and test. Table 1 presents research instruments and indicators for data collection at every stage.

Table 1. Research instruments and indicators

Instruments	Stages	Indicators	Respondents
Observation	Analysis	Stages of learning, educational books, materials, teaching methods, involvement, reading literacy, evaluation	Students Teachers
	Implementation	Educational tasks and phases, involvement and engagement, proficiency in reading, challenges and endeavors	Students Teachers
Interview Questionnaire	Analysis	Lacks, necessities, wants	Students
	Analysis	Lacks, necessities, wants	Students
Test	Implementation	Teaching materials, learning tasks, teaching materials, and assistance	Teachers
	Evaluation	Understanding and acquiring language skills, maintaining discipline, and enhancing reading comprehension contribute to the overall learning experience	Students

3. RESULTS

3.1. Need analysis of teaching materials

The process of obtaining needs analysis involved observing classroom learning, conducting interview with teachers, and using questionnaires to gather information from students. The goal was to understand the requirements for teaching materials requested by both teachers and students.

3.1.1. Learning observation results

Classroom observations are conducted to gather information on how the teacher is facilitating the learning process. The results of the learning observations are shown in Table 2. According to the data provided in the table, the mean score for English learning falls between 2.1 and 3.0, meeting the category for being considered good. This indicates that the teacher's English learning process has been successful but can be enhanced in various ways. For example, in the building knowledge of the field (BKoF) stage, the teacher did not accurately communicate the learning goals or connect the grammar material to previous lessons and the students' everyday lives. During the modelling of the text (MoT) stage, there were still students who did not have electronic devices. As a result, a few of them decided to gather with their friends to view the content using their own gadgets. At the joint construction of the text (JCoT), groups engage in discussions during the game as part of their learning activities. However, these discussions have not been assigned a specific allocation. At the individual construction of the text (ICoT), teacher did not engage in any tasks or exercises.

In terms of textbooks, teacher had not incorporated any extra or supplementary materials, such as modules or similar materials. In terms of the learning materials, teacher had not integrated them with the local content specific to the Jepara. The language learning method used by teacher was still divided between skills and had not yet been incorporated together. The engagement of students in classroom learning appeared satisfactory, although there were still a few students who lack proper focus and instead spent their time playing by themselves. Collaboration among students was only evident during classroom game activities. There were no activities in the reading aspect that require students to read longer texts, such as descriptive, recount, or narrative texts. In terms of assessment, teacher had not utilized organized assessments, such as assigning exercises or other tasks.

Table 2. Results of learning observation

No	Indicators	Score obtained
1	Stages of learning English	9
2	Textbook	8
3	Material	5
4	Learning approach	7
5	Participation	6
6	Reading literacy	3
7	Assessment	3
	Sum	41
	Mean	2.15
	Category	Good

3.1.2. Interview results

Two English teachers, teaching seventh grade students, were randomly selected for interviews. The interview markers pertain to Hutchinson and Waters' theory [36], which includes elements relating to lacks, necessities, and wants. In terms of lacks, the interview findings indicate that the current textbooks have deficiencies. These include the failure to incorporate students' local and regional culture, inadequacy in language skills, particularly in the areas of viewing and presenting, low participation, and a lack of a comprehensive approach to reading literacy competency. In terms of necessities, it was found that textbooks are still necessary but should be supplemented with additional materials to enhance learning. It is also important to integrate local and regional content alongside national and global material. Language skills should be presented in a holistic way, and learning activities should be focused and goal-oriented. In terms of the teacher's desires, they want the educational materials to promote a comprehensive understanding of reading skills by incorporating relevant local topics, such as influential figures like RA Kartini and Ratu Kalinyamat, notable places like Bandengan and Kartini beach and Manik cave, and traditional cuisine like *horog-horog*, *pindang serani*, and *adon-adon coro*, into the teaching materials.

3.1.3. Questionnaire results

The questionnaire in this study aimed to assess two main factors. They are target situation analysis (TSA) which included identifying the needs and lacks of teaching materials and learning need analysis

(LNA) which included identifying the preferences for teaching materials. The TSA questionnaire analysis provides information on the needs and lacks of teaching materials as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of questionnaire for necessities and lacks

No	Indicators Necessities	Mean	P (%)	Indicators Lacks	Mean	P (%)
1	Teaching materials is essential	3.2	78.9	The content found in current textbooks only encompasses aspects of both Indonesian national and international culture	3.2	79.6
2	Convenient in utilizing textbooks	3.3	82.2	The current textbook lacks information about the Jepara region's local content	3.1	79.6
3	Teaching materials assists in the process of learning English	3.2	78.9	The learning tasks in teaching materials are usually completed on student's own without assistance	2.9	74.8
4	I am interested in learning through local culture and context	3.3	81.4	There are no activities where pairs or groups work together	3.0	75
5	Local culture enhances my English-speaking abilities	2.9	74.5	The language skills material is given in a distinct manner	3.0	75.1
6	Teaching materials can enhance my overall reading skills	3.0	75.4	Teaching materials currently do not mention the conversation or discussion present in a text	2.4	60.9
7	Teaching materials that prioritize a comprehensive approach to reading are beneficial in improving my English language skills	3.0	76.4	The challenge in comprehending educational materials arises from a lack of familiarity with the specific situation and cultural background	2.8	71.2
	Mean Category	3.1 Need development	78.2	Mean Category	2.9 Need development	73.4

The average value obtained for the necessities indicator was 3.1 and for the lacks indicator it was 2.9, then clarified with the product development decision criteria. Because the average value of 3.1 is in the range of 3.0 to 4.0 and 2.9 is in the range of 2.0 to 3.0, then based on the indicators of needs (necessities) and weaknesses (lacks) teaching materials need to be developed. Based on Table 3, most students understand that teaching materials are important to use in learning English (3.2) because it makes it easy for them to learn English (3.3). Besides that, the use of teaching materials as additional learning materials helps students learn English (3.2). Students need teaching materials that contain material in accordance with the context of the local (cultural) content material (3.3). By understanding local culture, students can help them to speak English well (2.9). Besides that, students also need teaching materials that helping them to improve holistic reading literacy competencies through understanding the discourse of a text, both spoken and written (3.0) and holistic reading literacy (discourse) can help them in learning English (3.0).

According to the information provided in the table, English learning materials used by teachers and students currently only consist of national culture as the source culture and international culture as the target culture. However, these materials do not incorporate any elements of the local content or culture specific to the students' region. Specifically, the Jepara Regency has a rating of 3.1 and the text indicates that most learning activities in this area are performed individually or independently by students, with a rating of 2.9. Furthermore, there is still a lack of diversity in the ways activities are presented, specifically in terms of promoting collaboration and cooperation in pairs or groups (3.0). The presentation of language skills material in textbooks, be it worksheet or others, continues to remain separate and does not yet include references to discourse. A text can be in the form of either spoken or written communication (2.4). This leads to students struggling to understand the studying materials because they lack knowledge about the situational and cultural context of the text.

There are certain preferences when it comes to teaching materials. The type of material that students prefer is content that is focused on Jepara Regency, which accounts for 73.4% of their choice. They also desire Indonesian national content, which makes up 16.4%, and global content, which totals 10.1%. The requested groups of content are: i) individual's personality traits (72.6); ii) captivating locations (63.9); and iii) objects (things) encompassing food, beverages, and miscellaneous items (67.7). Additionally, the material that is wanted consists of discussions that talk about the specific circumstances and style (69.2) or various forms of texts that elaborate on the societal background (68.3). The teaching material should consist of material presentation (94.9%) such as text, pictures, tables, and graphs, as well as learning activities (96.8%) and exercises (91.1%). Activities in teaching materials are displayed in a collaborative manner for the majority (86%), while a smaller portion (13.9%) are presented in a contrasting, non-collaborative way. Collaborative or cooperative activities involve pairs of friends (62.6) and small groups (72.2) working

together. However, when it comes to English language skills, there is a combination of integrated (72.6) and separate (27.8) presentation of these skills. The combination of these abilities was demonstrated through listening and speaking, reading and viewing, and writing and presenting (82.3%), whereas the remaining percentage disagreed (17.1%). In addition, students desire teaching materials that are presented in a cultural context or genre that helps them comprehend the language and content of a text, whether it is spoken or written. The majority of students (75.9%) agree with this, while the remaining students (24.1%) disagree.

The findings of this study align with the research carried out by others researchers, who employed TSA and LNA to identify the requirements for teaching materials [37], [38]. Furthermore, incorporating culturally relevant materials related to students and their everyday experiences can help address their difficulties in understanding during the learning process [39]. This identification leads to a precise analysis in aligning the necessary teaching materials by taking into account the needs, lacks, and preferences.

3.2. Development of teaching materials

This phase involves identifying the desired respondents based on two factors. They are the ability to comprehend various types of text, both spoken and written, and to respond appropriately; and the proficiency in languages on a broader scale, comprehension of different text types, conveying special messages and information, and visual skills. The subsequent phase involves identifying the desired outcomes of learning, such as the development of skills in listening and speaking, reading and viewing, and writing and practicing. Afterward, the learning goals and teaching materials were organized and can be observed in Table 4. The following step involves an evaluation of the product carried out by lecturers and practitioners. The group of lecturers includes two academics specializing in English language education, while the practitioners are comprised of two seventh-grade English teachers. The result of experts' validation is presented in Table 5.

Table 4. Teaching materials mapping

Chapter	Unit	Materials
The first step	Jepara's important days	Numbers, dates, months and the members of the family and their job
	My families and their jobs	Family members and occupation
Nice to meet your	I am from Jepara	Asking and giving information and introduction of oneself and others
	The inspirational woman from Jepara	Describing characteristics (someone's physical features, personality traits, facts; such as job, age, hobby, and regular activities) of heroines in Jepara
My favorite culinary	I like <i>horog-horog</i>	Social function, generic structure and language features of procedure text
	Let's make our typical foods	Asking and giving information about food
Home	My Joglo Jepara House	Social function, generic structure and language features of procedure text
	Daily activities in Jepara	Rooms in a house
	Joglo house	Common activities that take place in each room, as well as the materials commonly found in those rooms
School activities	Class schedule	School subjects and class schedule
	Study habits	Students study habits
My city	Where is Kartini beach?	Location of place and practicing expression of asking and giving direction
	Jepara's festivals	Jepara's festival

Table 5. Experts' validation

No	Aspects	Score			
		Lecturer 1	Lecturer 2	Practitioner 1	Practitioner 2
1	Presentation	22	20	22	22
2	Materials	27	25	27	26
3	Language	23	20	23	21
4	Assistance	32	31	35	34
	Total	104	96	107	103
	Mean	3.71	3.42	3.82	3.67
	Total mean	3.56		3.74	
	Criteria	Very feasible		Very feasible	

According to the table provided, the average overall assessment for product validation among lecturers was 3.56, while for practitioners it was 3.74. The average value was subsequently transferred to the validation product criteria retrieval table. The overall assessment scores of 3.56 and 3.74 fall within the range of 3.0 to 4.0, indicating that the teaching materials created by the researcher are deemed very feasible. Nonetheless, the recommendations and feedback for enhancement given by both practitioners were addressed by organizing a focus group discussion to refine the teaching materials. Product updates encompass the cover, design, dimensions, images, activities, and book indexing.

The ADDIE design model for product development involves extensive stages, primarily focusing on the design and development phases, which create prototypes based on a needs analysis [16], [40]. The content in the developed teaching materials should encourage students to be motivated to learn [41], engage in interactions through language skills [16], and incorporate local cultural values along with the target values of the language being taught [27], [42]. Visual representations of cultural context can help students better understand the characters within that context [43].

3.3. Practicality of teaching materials

The practicality of the teaching material is evaluated through observations made by teachers, who aim to assess the local content materials developed by the researcher. Table 6 indicates that the researcher's learning process has been effective, as they have successfully implemented BKoF, MoT, JCoT, and ICoT. Learning activities are effectively designed by utilizing teaching materials and incorporating collaborative elements. Reading literacy has also been developed by combining various skills. Researchers could expect to encounter different challenges that occur during the learning process. The overall score of 58 is divided by all components of the indicator, which adds up to 17, resulting in an average of 3.4. The average falls between 3.1 and 4.0, indicating that learning English with local content-based teaching materials using the ICL approach is classified as very good.

Table 6. Observation result

No	Indicators	Score
1	Learning phases	3
2	Learning processes	14
3	Educational activities	11
4	Engagement and involvement	6
5	Reading literacy	10
6	Challenges	7
7	Attempts to address challenges	7
	Total score	58
	Mean	3.4
	Criteria	Very good

The average score of 3.21 is assessed using the criteria determination table, categorizing the developed teaching materials as very practical. This is illustrated in Table 7, which shows a mean of 3.30 for the content indicator, 3.29 for the supporting indicator, 3.25 for the teaching material indicator, and 2.98 for the activity indicator. As a result, students have responded positively to the teaching materials, viewing them as practical for classroom learning.

During the implementation, students responded positively to the developed materials in various aspects. The students' feedback comprised various elements such as teaching materials, activities, subject matter, and assistance. This aligns with earlier studies that demonstrate how teaching materials rooted in local wisdom can enhance students' awareness of local culture [44] and the values embodied within it [15]. Indeed, utilizing local regional materials for learning English is a viable option for enhancing English education with a global perspective [12]. In addition, it can enhance awareness of different cultures in language learning [43].

Table 7. Practicality score

No	Indicator	Mean
1	Teaching materials	3.25
2	Activities	2.98
3	Contents	3.30
4	Supporting	3.29
	Mean	3.21
	Criteria	Very practical

3.4. The effectiveness of teaching materials

The effectiveness of the teaching materials was assessed through tests conducted on a larger sample. The researcher carried out an experiment in a test group utilizing local content-based teaching materials, while a control group used standard teaching materials. The trial took place over three meetings. The mean score for class VII A, designated as the experimental group, is 67.87, which is higher than the mean score of 60.96 for class VII B, the control group. This indicates that the overall reading literacy of class VII A

improved after being taught with local content-based materials, in contrast to class VII B, which utilized only conventional textbooks. Moreover, advancements can also be observed in the holistic reading skills metrics presented in the Table 8.

According to the table, the overall holistic reading average score for class VII A, the experimental class, was higher than that of class VII B, the control class. The distinction lies in the learning experience related to language abilities, communication, and reading understanding. This indicates that the created teaching materials can enhance students' holistic reading skills comprehensively. This aligns with the research which demonstrates that holistic reading produces consistent learning outcomes because students can learn from cultural and situation contexts [45]. Teachers play a crucial role in enhancing students' overall skills based on their knowledge and experience [11].

Table 8. Students holistic reading

No	Indicators	Sub-indicators	Score	
			VII A	VII B
1	Learning experiences through language skills	Spoken skills	61.63	54.98
		Written skills	65.21	65.21
2	Discourse of the text	Jepara local content	59.83	52.58
		Daily activities	60.32	55.25
3	Reading comprehension	Vocabulary mastery	66.66	65.21
		Identifying main purpose	63.76	60.86
		Skimming of the text	68.11	58.69
		Scanning of the text	70.75	60.05
		Structures understanding	60.86	57.97
		Predicting of the text	72.46	58.69

4. DISCUSSION

The aim of learning English extends beyond just familiarizing students with the target culture; it also seeks to help them understand local or national cultures [46]. This creates a chance to develop teaching materials by taking into account materials from the local content [41], [47]. This advancement must be executed with accurate mapping that takes into account the needs, weaknesses, and preferences [36] of both students and teachers. Incorporating local content into teaching materials can enhance students' learning of English by offering them insights into local culture and the values associated with it [48]. Additionally, it can help students enhance their language abilities by allowing them to delve into their comprehension of local cultural content [49]. Local content material encompasses information about: i) the challenges faced by notable figures like RA Kartini, known for her fight for women's rights, and *Ratu Kalinyamat*, recognized for her resistance against colonial forces; ii) well-known locations such as Bandengan Beach and Manik Cave; iii) traditional dishes and beverages like *adon-adon coro* and *horog-horog*; and iv) the activities and professions of the local people, including *troso* weavers, *monel* craftsmen, woodcarvers, fishermen, and more [50]. The findings of this study align with previous research highlighting the occupations within the Jepara community, the struggle of certain individuals, historically significant locations, and the region's characteristic food and beverages [18]–[20].

The local content in the teaching materials is delivered through a variety of learning activities, including collaboration and teamwork in pairs and small groups. Language skills are integrated across different forms, encompassing various types of texts such as dialogues, monologues, and both oral and written formats. The material was well-received, as it demonstrated an enhancement in students' holistic reading skills. Incorporating local culture into education helps students grasp global culture [14], and this approach is enhanced when it is woven into both co-curricular and intra-curricular activities [48]. Locally provided language skills materials assist students in enhancing their spoken [51] and written abilities [29], [47], [52]. Combining oral skills, such as listening and speaking [53], with written skills like reading and writing [54], [55], yields beneficial outcomes, particularly in enhancing the overall language learning experience. The outcome of this integration leads to a holistic understanding, enhanced learning advantages, genuine materials, and increased student engagement [56]. Conversely, it can enhance knowledge, foster understanding among participants, and encourage students to engage actively [57].

Furthermore, students' holistic reading skills are demonstrated through their understanding of a text's discourse. Grasping the discourse of a text involves recognizing the context of the student's environment, which is abundant in local knowledge and positive values [44], thereby fostering student engagement in the learning process [58], [59]. Moreover, comprehending daily activities enhances students' communication skills, as these actions are performed consistently [39] and encourage contextual learning to develop students engagement [60]. Besides that, the enhancement of holistic reading skills following the introduction of teaching materials centered on local content also aligns with findings from other researches.

Consequently, this study suggests that the Department of National Education and Regional Education Offices may utilize locally sourced materials to enhance students' understanding in a way that relates to their everyday experiences, thereby fostering their holistic reading comprehension skills.

5. CONCLUSION

The identification of teaching material requirements using TSA and LNA offers a thorough assessment of the materials, activities, and skills outlined in the teaching materials. This is due to the analysis identifying both the needs and shortcomings of current teaching materials, as well as the types of materials that students prefer. Teaching materials that focus on local content from the students' surroundings are very important to increase the activeness and experience of learning English, which will have a positive impact on learning competence and achievement, including holistic reading skills. The teaching materials are created by combining language skills, facilitating collaborative learning activities, and incorporating local content from Jepara, which includes notable figures, locations, food and beverages, as well as activities of Jepara community. The teaching materials created received a positive evaluation from the experts participating in the assessment. This indicates that the teaching materials can be utilized in extensive experiment. Utilizing teaching materials that focus on local content could enhance students' holistic reading skills, as demonstrated by improvements in language proficiency, text discourse, and reading comprehension. This study recommends that government policies through the Department of National Education should be created to encourage the use of local materials in language learning, in order to promote awareness of local culture. For future studies, it would be beneficial to carry out an effectiveness evaluation to examine how teaching materials influence other variables.

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Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Husni Mubarok	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
Sofyan Anif	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				✓		✓		
Harun Joko Prayitno	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				✓	✓			

C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : Writing - Review & **E**ditng

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

INFORMED CONSENT

We have obtained informed consent from all individuals included in this study.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The authors confirm that the needs analysis data supporting the findings of this study are accessible in the article at <https://doi.org/10.36941/jesr-2024-0102>, and the full data findings are available to the corresponding author [HM], upon reasonable request.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Husni Mubarak is currently pursuing a doctorate in the field of education at the Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta, Indonesia. In addition to being a student, he also works as a lecturer at the English Language Education study program at the Universitas Islam Nahdlatul Ulama Jepara, Indonesia. He has been awarded numerous researches and services grants from external sources like the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology and the Ministry of Religion. In addition to that, he has also produced written materials such as journal articles, books, and copyrighted works. These can be found by referring to SINTA, the Ministry of Education and Culture, and Research and Technology. He can be contacted at email: q300230002@student.ums.ac.id.

Sofyan Anif is first advisor in providing guidance to the first author who conducts the research and writes article. He works as a lecturer and a professor in the faculty of teacher training and education at the Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta (UMS), Indonesia. At the moment, he holds the position of UMS rector. The area in which he specializes in education, therefore a large portion of his researches and services are focused on education. In addition to that, he has also written numerous articles for international journals. He can be contacted at email: sa163@ums.ac.id.

Harun Joko Prayitno acts as a second advisor and provides guidance to the first author throughout the research and writing process for the article. He is a professor and teaches Indonesian language and literature education at the Teacher Training and Education at the Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta, Indonesia. At present, he holds the position of vice rector for academic affairs at the university. In addition to publishing articles in international journals, he also conducts extensive researches in the field of language education and holistic teaching and learning. He can be contacted at email: hjp220@ums.ac.id.